

XtalFluor-E: A useful and versatile reagent in organic transformations

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Abstract

XtalFluor-E, [Et₂NSF₂]BF₄, is best known as a useful, versatile and inexpensive commercially available reagent for the deoxyfluorination of carbonyl compounds and alcohols. Although XtalFluor-E is commonly used in combination with an exogenous fluoride source as a deoxofluorinating reagent, it has also been widely employed in other chemical transformations such as dehydration, cyclodehydration, ring expansion, formylation, and proto-functionalization, etc. This Review aims to provide an overview for the applications of XtalFluor-E as a reagent in organic synthesis, including its physical properties, futures, and its unique roles beyond than being just as a deoxofluorinating reagent in organic transformation.

Keywords: XtalFluor-E, [Et₂NSF₂]BF₄, Reagent, Deoxofluorination, Dehydration, Halogenation